

Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) Complexes of Dopamine and Isoprenaline

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Conductometric and spectrophotometric studies indicate formation of (M:L) 1:1 and 1:2 complexes between Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and the two ligands Dopamine and Isoprenaline. The stepwise and the overall stability constants have been calculated and the thermodynamic parameters, ΔG , ΔH and ΔS , have been worked out at three temperatures 0°, 25° and 37° and a fixed ionic strength of 0.1M with KCl. The order of stability was found to vary as Cu(II) > Ni(II) \approx Co(II). Structures of the complexes isolated have also been proposed on the basis of the analytical data and IR spectra.

CATECHOL amines include important drugs used as vasopressors, bronchodilators, circulatory stimulants and local vasoconstrictors. Many normal and transition elements are found to form complexes with phenol and phenolic amines¹. Noradrenaline and Adrenaline complexes of many transition elements have been reported²⁻⁸ in the literature. In the present communication is reported a study of the complexes of Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) with Dopamine and Isoprenaline.

Experimental

High purity grade chemicals were used. Cu(II), Co(II) and Ni(II) chlorides were of A. R. (BDH) grade. Stock solutions were prepared in double distilled water and were standardised by standard methods. Dopamine hydrochloride (Rhein, Germany) and Isoprenaline (Burroughs Wellcom Ltd., India) were dissolved in deionised boiled water. 1 ml of 2N HCl/100 ml solution for the experimental solution was added to check the hydrolysis.

Stoichiometry: Stoichiometry of the complexes formed was ascertained by spectrophotometric and conductometric studies.

The spectrophotometric measurements were carried out with "Spekol" (Carl Zena Zesis, Germany) using the cells of the length 5 cm. The solutions of the ligands and the metal salts were diluted to required concentrations and mixed in the metal : ligand ratio of 2:1, 1:1 and 1:2 and the absorbance was noted at different wavelengths.

Absorbance suggested a single maxima at 355 m μ for all the three Dopamine-metal systems; while for Isoprenaline-Cu(II) and Co(II) systems λ_{max} was found to be at 410 m μ and 350 m μ respectively. Job's

method of continuous variation⁹ (applied with two concentrations 0.0004 M and 0.0005 M) indicated formation of 1:2 (M:L) complexes with these ligands and the metals.

The conductometric studies were carried out with the Toshniwal Conductivity Bridge using dip-type conductivity cell (having a cell constant 0.42). 10 ml of the ligand solution (0.01 M) was diluted to 100 ml and was titrated with 0.01 M metal solution. The conductances were recorded after each addition of 0.5 ml of the metal solution and were corrected to the dilution effect. The plots of conductance vs volume of the metal added indicated formation of two 1:1 and 1:2 (M:L) complexes with these metals and the ligands.

Stability and Thermodynamic constants :

Calvin-Bjerrum's method¹⁰ as adopted by Irving and Rossotti¹¹ has been utilised to calculate stepwise and the overall "Formation constants" at three temperatures 0°, 25° and 37° and at a fixed ionic strength of 0.1 M with KCl. The experimental procedure consists in titration of the following thermostated mixtures of solutions with a 0.2 M alkali solution and recording the pH reading after each addition of 0.05 ml of the alkali :

- (i) Mixture (A) : 5 ml of (0.002 M) HCl solution.
- (ii) Mixture (B) : Mixture (A) + 10 ml of (0.001 M) Ligand (Dopamine or Isoprenaline)
- (iii) Mixture (C) : Mixture (B) + 5 ml of (0.005 M) metal solution.

The ionic strength of the above solutions was maintained to 0.1 M by adding the required quantity of 1.0 M KCl solution, keeping the total volume 50 ml with double distilled water.

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TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS, DOPAMINE COMPLEXES—
 $\mu = 0.1 M$ (KCl)

S.No.	Metal ion	Temp. °C	log K_1	log K_2	log $K_1 \cdot K_2$	log β_2 (Overall)
1.	Cu(II)	0	9.500 (10.78)	1.000 (4.67)	15.500 (15.47)	15.200 (15.48)
		25	9.100 (9.79)	5.800 (4.43)	14.900 (14.22)	14.800 (14.24)
		37	8.100 (10.40)	5.250 (3.73)	13.350 (14.13)	13.100 (14.14)
2.	Ni(II)	0	6.123 (7.0)	3.650 (2.288)	9.773 (9.88)	9.400 (9.90)
		25	5.273 (6.60)	3.440 (2.26)	8.713 (8.86)	8.600 (8.86)
		37	4.580 (6.20)	3.350 (2.20)	7.930 (8.40)	7.700 (8.40)
3.	Co(II)	0	5.620 (6.41)	3.5 (2.70)	9.12 (9.11)	8.90 (9.12)
		25	5.150 (6.17)	3.15 (2.00)	8.30 (8.17)	8.10 (8.16)
		37	4.550 (5.52)	3.0 (1.81)	7.55 (7.33)	7.04 (7.34)

Note : Values given in the parenthesis are those obtained by Least Square Method.

TABLE 2—STABILITY CONSTANTS, ISOPRENALINE COMPLEXES—
 $\mu = 0.1 M$ (KCl)

S.No.	Metal ion	Temp. °C	Log K_1	Log K_2	log $K_1 \cdot K_2$	Log β_2 (Overall)
1.	Cu(II)	0	9.5 (11.05)	8.0 (6.29)	17.5 (17.34)	17.3 (17.34)
		25	9.45 (11.0)	7.2 (6.10)	16.65 (17.10)	16.5 (17.10)
		37	8.95 (10.59)	6.232 (4.71)	15.182 (15.30)	15.0 (15.30)
2.	Ni(II)	0	5.95 (6.64)	3.25 (2.64)	9.2 (9.48)	8.5 (9.48)
		25	5.7 (6.61)	3.2 (2.56)	8.9 (9.17)	8.2 (9.16)
		37	5.375 (6.38)	3.05 (2.21)	8.425 (8.59)	7.8 (8.58)
3.	Co(II)	0	5.2 (6.15)	3.0 (2.31)	8.2 (8.46)	8.0 (8.46)
		25	5.05 (6.11)	2.95 (2.14)	8.0 (8.25)	7.72 (8.26)
		37	4.90 (6.08)	2.8 (2.08)	7.70 (8.16)	7.30 (8.16)

Note : Values given in parenthesis are those obtained by the Least Square Method.

The values of $\bar{n}H$, \bar{n} and pL were calculated using the Irving-Rossotti equations¹¹ and the values of log

K_1 , log K_2 , log $K_1 \cdot K_2$ and log β_2 were recorded directly from the formation curves. The refined values for the same were computed by the best least square fits (Table 1 and 2).

The thermodynamic parameters computed for the complexation reactions studied in this investigation are free energy, enthalpy and entropy changes and have been calculated using the isotherm, the isobar and the Gibbs-Helmholtz's equations respectively at 25° and 37° and at a ionic strength of 0.1 M with KCl (Table 3).

A perusal of the Table 1 to 4 indicates the order of stability to vary as : Cu(II) > Ni(II) \approx Co(II), while that of ΔH as : Ni(II) > Cu(II) > Co(II). Andrews *et al*² have studied the stability of Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) complexes with Adrenaline and Noradrenaline. A comparison of the same with that obtained in the present investigation using Dopamine and Isoprenaline is given in Table 4, which clearly indicates that stability of the complexes with the ligands having secondary amino group is greater than that having primary amino group : (Isoprenaline > Dopamine, cf. Adrenaline > Noradrenaline).

Isolation and Composition :

Isolation of the complexes was done by refluxing equimolar solutions of the metal and the ligand in Metal : Ligand 1:2 ratio (Ligand in the slight excess than the stoichiometric ratio) for 5 hours. The solution was then concentrated to one fifth of the original volume on a water bath. The complex was then separated by vacuum drying in a vacuum dessicator. The excess of the ligand was removed by washing with absolute alcohol in which the complex dissolves leaving behind the uncomplexed ligand. The alcoholic solution is then dried under vacuum and pure complex was obtained. The composition of the different complexes has been ascertained by estimating the metal¹², nitrogen by semimicro Kjeldahl method¹³ and the quantity of water associated.

The physical properties of the complexes-isolated and their analytical data are recorded in Table 5. Based on the analytical data the composition of the complexes was found to be ML_2 with Cu(II) and Ni(II) and $ML_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ with Co(II).

IR Spectra :

The important IR frequencies (along with their assignments) recorded on Perkin Elmer infrared spectrophotometer, Model 237, for the complexes isolated indicate considerable change in the characteristic frequencies of -OH group in all the complexes of the ligands and hence the complexation may be considered to take through the phenolic hydroxyl groups, forming a five membered ring as suggested by Andrews *et al*² Further the potentiometric (pH) titrations indicated

TABLE 3—DATA ON STEPWISE AND OVERALL ENERGY OF FORMATION, LIGATIONAL ENTHALPES AND LIGATIONAL ENTROPIES OF COMPLEXES

Metal ion	Temp. °C	$-\Delta G_1$	$-\Delta G_2^{\ddagger}$	$-\Delta G_3$ (Overall)	$-\Delta H_1$	$-\Delta H_2^{\ddagger}$	$-\Delta H_3$ (Overall)	ΔS_1	ΔS_2	ΔS_3 (Overall)	
Cu(II)	0°	DA	11.942	7.542	19.106	—	—	—	—	—	
		IP	11.942	10.056	21.746	—	—	—	—	—	
	25°	DA	12.494	7.963	20.320	5.955	2.978	5.955	21.943	16.728	48.205
		IP	12.975	9.886	22.655	0.744	11.910	11.910	41.043	6.792	36.057
	37°	DA	11.567	7.497	18.707	14.65	7.848	21.974	-9.945	-1.178	-10.539
		IP	12.781	8.899	21.420	5.755	18.500	24.067	22.665	30.971	-8.539
Ni(II)	0°	DA	9.675	4.588	11.816	—	—	—	—	—	
		IP	7.479	4.085	10.685	—	—	—	—	—	
	25°	DA	7.240	4.723	11.808	12.655	3.126	11.190	-18.171	5.359	2.074
		IP	7.826	4.394	11.259	3.722	0.744	4.466	13.772	12.248	22.795
	37°	DA	6.54	4.784	10.996	15.146	3.139	17.789	-27.761	5.359	2.074
		IP	7.676	4.355	11.138	6.017	2.093	7.325	5.352	7.297	12.300
Co(II)	0°	DA	7.064	4.40	11.187	—	—	—	—	—	
		IP	6.536	3.771	10.056	—	—	—	—	—	
	25°	DA	7.071	4.325	11.121	6.997	5.211	11.910	0.248	-2.973	-2.648
		IP	6.934	4.050	10.60	2.233	0.744	4.169	15.775	11.094	21.580
	37°	DA	6.497	4.284	10.053	11.196	5.232	19.463	-15.158	-3.058	-30.355
		IP	6.997	3.998	10.424	3.139	2.093	7.325	12.445	6.145	9.997

DA = Dopamine ; IP = Isoprenaline.

 TABLE 4—COMPARISON OF STABILITY CONSTANTS—
 $\mu = 0.1 M$ (KCl)

Metal ion	Temperature	$\log K_1$			
		Ad ⁽²⁾	Na ⁽²⁾	DA	IP
Cu(II)	0°	10.96	10.25	9.50	9.50
	25°	10.50	9.13	9.10	9.45
Ni(II)	0°	6.17	5.76	6.123	5.95
	25°	5.62	5.28	5.273	5.70
Co(II)	0°	6.09	5.32	5.62	5.20
	25°	5.42	4.82	5.15	5.05

 Ad = Adrenaline
 NA = Noradrenaline
 DA = Dopamine
 IP = Isoprenaline

liberation of only one proton during the complexation of each molecule of the ligand. Hence, considering the coordination numbers of the metals, Cu(II) and Ni(II)=4 and Co(II)=6, and the analytical data the following general structures may be proposed for the complexes studied in this investigation :

 $R = \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{NH}_2$ in Dopamine

 $= \text{CH}(\text{OH}) \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{NH} \cdot \text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$ in Isoprenaline.

 $M = \text{Co(II)}, \text{Ni(II)} \text{ or } \text{Cu(II)}$.

The remaining coordination positions in Co(II) complexes are filled with two H_2O moles. This finds

TABLE 5—PHYSICAL PROPERTIES AND THE ANALYTICAL DATA

Complex	Properties	% Metal		% N		% H ₂ O	
		T	F	T	F	T	F
1. Cu(C ₈ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂)	Dark Brown powder, hygroscopic, highly soluble in H ₂ O and alcohol, m.p. 186°.	17.279	17.135	07.619	7.523	-	-
2. Co(C ₈ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Pinkish Red, crystalline, nonhygroscopic, soluble in H ₂ O and alcohol, m.p. 192°.	14.774	14.576	7.019	7.001	9.024	8.992
3. Ni(C ₈ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂) ₂	Bluish Violet, crystalline, non-hygroscopic, soluble in water and alcohol, m.p. 189°.	16.184	16.004	7.72	7.810	-	-
4. Cu(C ₁₁ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₂) ₂	Dark Brown, hygroscopic, highly soluble in water and alcohol, m.p. 195°.	13.133	13.10	5.791	5.659	-	-
5. Co(C ₁₁ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₂) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Bluish Violet, hygroscopic, highly soluble in H ₂ O and alcohol, m.p. 172°.	11.446	11.506	5.437	5.321	6.991	6.973
6. Ni(C ₁₁ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₂) ₂	Greenish Brown, hygroscopic, highly soluble in H ₂ O and alcohol, m.p. 186°.	12.262	12.14	5.849	5.792	-	-

confirmation in the presence of the bands at frequencies 3600 – 3200 and 880 – 650 in IR spectra of the Co(II) complexes studied here.

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